

TABLE I—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [REACTANTS] ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

(a=25°, b=30°, c=40° and d=45°)

[K ₂ Fe(ON) ₆] × 10 ³ M	[4-ABA] × 10 ³ M	[Ru(III)] × 10 ³ M	[NaOH] × 10 ³ M	(-dc/dt) × 10 ³ mole lit ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
1.00	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.54
1.25	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.60
1.43	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.45
1.67	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.47
2.00	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.50
2.50	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.40
1.25	0.40	1.91	1.00	4.00*
1.25	0.50	1.91	1.00	5.05*
1.25	0.67	1.91	1.00	5.66*
1.25	1.00	1.91	1.00	6.00*
1.25	1.43	1.91	1.00	6.04*
1.25	2.00	1.91	1.00	5.60*
1.25	1.00	0.76	1.00	1.60
1.25	1.00	1.58	1.00	3.00
1.25	1.00	2.29	1.00	4.30
1.25	1.00	2.67	1.00	5.20
1.25	1.00	3.06	1.00	6.25
1.25	1.00	3.82	1.00	7.10
1.25	0.67	1.91	0.50	4.00**
1.25	0.67	1.91	0.66	5.02**
1.25	0.67	1.91	1.00	8.60**
1.25	0.67	1.91	1.35	12.46**
1.25	0.67	1.91	1.66	14.40**
1.25	0.67	1.91	2.00	17.96**
1.25	1.00	1.91	1.00	0.74 ^a
1.25	1.00	1.91	1.00	1.07 ^b
1.25	1.00	1.91	1.00	2.80 ^c
1.25	1.00	1.91	1.00	4.17 ^d

[4-ABA]=[4-Aminobutyric acid], μ=0.2M, *μ=0.8M, **μ=1.0M
Ionic strength (μ) was varied by addition of suitable amounts of sodium perchlorate.

Applying steady state treatment to the complex (C₁) and knowing that [Ru(III)]_T = [Ru(III)] + [Complex C₁], the rate law could be obtained as

$$\frac{-d[\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{4k_1k_2K_1[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Ru(III)}]_T}{(k_{-1} + k_2) + k_1K_1[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]} \dots \text{(2)}$$

where K₁ = K/[H₂O]

At low concentrations of 4-aminobutyric acid the inequality k₋₁ + k₂ ≫ k₁K₁[S][OH⁻] holds good and eq (2) reduces to eq (3)

$$\frac{-d[\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{4k_1k_2K_1[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Ru(III)}]_T}{k_{-1} + k_2} \text{ (3)}$$

which clearly explains the first-order kinetics with respect to 4-aminobutyric acid at lower concentrations and first-order dependence on [OH⁻] and

[Ru(III)]. At constant [OH⁻] and higher [S] the inequality k₁K₁[S][OH⁻] ≫ k₋₁ + k₂ would exist resulting in a zero-order dependence on [4-aminobutyric acid] which has been observed in the present work.

At constant [OH⁻] the plot of 1/V₁ (where V₁ = -d[Fe(CN)₆³⁻]/dt) against 1/[S] gave a straight line with positive intercept on 1/V₁ axis, satisfying the Michaelis-Menten type reciprocal relationship⁶ [a kinetic proof for complex formation between Ru(III) species and 4-aminobutyric acid prior to the rate determining step] and also confirming the validity of rate law (2).

Stoichiometry and product analysis: Different sets of reaction mixture containing known excess of hexacyanoferrate(III) over 4-aminobutyric acid were kept at 30° in presence of 0.01 M NaOH and 11.47 × 10⁻⁶ M Ru(III). The amount of hexacyanoferrate(III) left in all the cases were consistent with stoichiometric eq (4).

Succinic acid was identified as reaction product by chromatographic technique.

Acknowledgement

The authors thankfully acknowledge the financial assistance from C.S.I.R., New Delhi.

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Stability Constants of the Complexes of Substituted Salicylic Acids with Co(II) and Ni(II)

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Manuscript received 14 April 1982, accepted 23 April 1983

COMPLEXES of salicylic acid and various substituted salicylic acids have been extensively studied, mostly by pH-potentiometric method. While most of these workers¹ have reported the formation

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TABLE 1—TEMPERATURE $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Sl. No.	Ligand	Log K_{COOH}^H	Log K_{OH}^H	Log K^{Co}	Log K^{Ni}	Log K^{Cu}
1.	Phenol	—	10.00	—	—	—
2.	Salicylic acid	2.97 ± 0.02 (240 nm; 0.0001 M)	18.8 ^a	8.09 ± 0.03 (340 nm; 0.0321 M)	8.17 ± 0.04 (340 nm; 0.033 M)	10.67 ± 0.03 (240 nm; 0.033 M)
3.	3-Nitro-salicylic acid	1.82 ± 0.02 (440 nm; 0.002 M)	10.25 ± 0.02 (550 nm; 0.002 M)	5.76 ± 0.04 (440 nm; 0.0035 M)	5.89 ± 0.04 (440 nm; 0.0037 M)	8.44 ± 0.04 (470 nm; 0.0031 M)
4.	4-Nitro-salicylic acid	1.43 ± 0.02 (420 nm; 0.001 M)	10.32 ± 0.02 (440 nm; 0.00056 M)	5.37 ± 0.04 (430 nm; 0.01 M)	5.46 ± 0.04 (430 nm; 0.006 M)	7.43 ± 0.04 (430 nm; 0.006 M)
5.	5-Chloro-salicylic acid	2.71 ± 0.02 (344 nm; 0.001 M)	12.22 ± 0.02 (346 nm; 0.001 M)	6.43 ± 0.08 (350 nm; 0.00841 M)	6.49 ± 0.03 (350 nm; 0.00841 M)	9.66 ± 0.11 (346 nm; 0.0051 M)
6.	5-Bromo-salicylic acid	2.61 ± 0.04 (340 nm; 0.0008 M)	12.11 ± 0.05 (344 nm; 0.001 M)	6.43 ± 0.04 (346 nm; 0.016 M)	6.48 ± 0.03 (346 nm; 0.013 M)	9.37 ± 0.08 (346 nm; 0.0072 M)
7.	5-Sulpho-salicylic acid	2.87 ± 0.04 (342 nm; 0.02 M)	11.77 ± 0.01 (342 nm; 0.0048 M)	6.12 ± 0.09 (344 nm; 0.05 M)	6.14 ± 0.09 (344 nm; 0.038 M)	8.36 ± 0.11 (344 nm; 0.0176 M)
8.	3,5-Dinitro-salicylic acid	1.52 ± 0.03 (410 nm; 0.002 M)	7.01 ± 0.04 (470 nm; 0.0002 M)	3.82 ± 0.06 (400 nm; 0.001 M)	4.13 ± 0.12 (400 nm; 0.001 M)	6.68 ± 0.07 (370 nm; 0.00044 M)
9.	Azo-salicylic acid	2.26 ± 0.02 (400 nm; 0.00008 M)	11.26 ± 0.03 (460 nm; 0.00003 M)	6.01 ± 0.03 (450 nm; 0.00155 M)	6.23 ± 0.04 (450 nm; 0.0006 M)	9.11 ± 0.04 (450 nm; 0.0007 M)
10.	4-Methyl-azo-salicylic acid	2.45 ± 0.04 (410 nm; 0.0001 M)	11.45 ± 0.06 (470 nm; 0.00002 M)	5.54 ± 0.06 (460 nm; 0.00115 M)	6.39 ± 0.06 (460 nm; 0.00128 M)	10.31 ± 0.06 (420 nm; 0.00062 M)
11.	3'-Nitro-azo-salicylic acid	2.16 ± 0.03 (410 nm; 0.00008 M)	11.15 ± 0.03 (510 nm; 0.00006 M)	6.03 ± 0.02 (460 nm; 0.00065 M)	6.88 ± 0.04 (460 nm; 0.00061 M)	10.14 ± 0.04 (460 nm; 0.00067 M)

(Values given in the parenthesis are of respective wave length and ionic strength at which the studies have been made).

of only 1 : 1 complexes with transition metal ions Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II), some^{1a} have reported the formation of 1 : 2 complexes with Cu(II). While some have reported^{1a} the formation of 1 : 2 complexes in the case of 3-nitrosalicylic acid even with Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II), others have disputed² the formation of 1 : 2 complexes with Cu(II). In view of these reports, we decided to study these complexes by spectrophotometric methods. Whereas ionization of the phenolic hydrogen of salicylic acid can complicate the results of the pH-potentiometric studies and sometimes precipitation of hydroxo-complexes or hydroxides can also be missed, these difficulties are completely eliminated in the spectrophotometric method. The spectra of the salicylic acids and their 1 : 1 complexes can first be studied by taking the acids alone, and also with an excess of metal ion. The presence of any 1 : 2 or higher complexes can easily be inferred by any deviation from the additivity rule when large excess of the salicylic acids is used. In fact, the superiority of the spectrophotometric method in suitable cases has already been acknowledged³.

The ligands studied herein are salicylic acid and its 5-chloro-, 5-bromo-, 5-sulpho-, 3-nitro-, 4-nitro- and 3,5-dinitro derivatives. Metal ions used are Co(II) and Ni(II).

Experimental

Materials and methods :

These have already been described in detail earlier⁴. The computations of the first and second proton stability constant⁵ and the first metal stability constants⁶, were by spectrophotometric methods. Conductance measurements were made with a Philips GM 4144 bridge at $32 \pm 0.1^\circ$ on a

series of solutions prepared as per Job's method⁷ in order to bring out relationship between complex formation and deviation from additivity in conductance, since it has an important bearing on the structure of the complex (Table 2).

TABLE 2—CONDUCTOMETRIC STUDIES ON COMPLEX FORMING REACTIONS

(Job's Method of Continuous Variations)

Ligand—3-Nitrosalicylic acid ; Metal ion—Ni(II) ;
Strength of each solution—0.004 M ; Solvent—water
pH of each solution before mixing—7.00 ;
Temp. $32 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Conductance (mho $\times 10^3$)

1	2	3	4	5	6
V (ml)	V ml ligand + (20-V) ml of metal ion	Ligand blank [V ml ligand + (20-V) ml water]	Metal blank [V ml water + (20-V) ml metal ion]	Sum of ligand and metal blanks	Deviation from additivity : Column 5-Column 3
2	877	67	823	890	13
4	852	119	758	877	25
6	815	166	685	851	36
8	771	206	610	816	45
10	725	250	526	776	51
12	695	298	442	740	45
14	648	380	350	680	37
16	614	390	250	640	26
18	560	425	148	573	13

Results and Discussion

The proton stability constants, K_1^H and K_2^H , and the metal stability constants, K_1^{Co} and K_1^{Ni} , of the salicylic acids obtained herein are given in Table 1. That no 1 : 2 complex was formed, could be seen from the fact that even when excess of ligand was used the calculation of K_1^{Co} or K_1^{Ni} showed no significant deviation. On using a ten-fold excess of metal ion, a value for E_1 could be calculated. When

the ratios were reversed, and the absorbance at the same wave-length and pH was observed with ten-fold excess of the ligand, it was found that the observed absorbance coincided with additive value calculated on the basis of the formation of 1:1 complex with excess of ligand remaining unchanged. The same had been found with Cu(II) also as reported earlier⁴.

As in the case of Cu(II), (*loc.cit.*), a rough linear relationship could be drawn between $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_1^M$. This is to be expected⁹ if the proton and metal stability constants are pictured as due to analogous equilibria between the completely ionized salicylate ions and proton or metal ions. This has resulted in the equilibria being often assumed⁹ to be:

This should result in a large increase in conductance because of the high mobility of H^+ ions. However, the data in Table 2 clearly show that the conductance actually falls on complex formation and the fall is proportional to the formation of 1:1 complex. Such conductance data as in Table 2 were found to be representative of all the three metal ions Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with all the ligands studied here. Hence, the equilibrium shown in (1) above, should be correctly shown as:

Out of the two structures, III would appear to be the more likely one as it would allow for the possibility of its stabilization by the following type of resonance, similar to that of the diketones⁸:

In a number of studies¹⁰ using a variety of method, the complexes of salicylic acids have been shown not to ionize off one of the hydrogens. Varma and Mehrotra¹¹ have shown that beryllium gives a complex without one of the hydrogens ionizing off, but the resulting complex had a $\log K_1^H$ of only 2.4, whereas salicylic acid has a $\log K_1^H$ of over 13. Such a large change in $\log K_1^H$ would be seen to confirm that III would be the more logical structure. Of course, with the transition metals which form dative $\text{d}\pi$ bonds¹² the $\log K_1^H$ of the resulting complexes would not drop down to low values as in the case of beryllium.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. K. S. Murty and Prof. N. L. Jain, Director, Technical Education, M. P. and Prof. C. K. Keswari, Principal, Govt. Engg. College, Sagar for permission and research facilities.

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Stability Constants of N-(2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene)-4-Carbomethoxyaniline with Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cd^{2+}

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Manuscript received 14 September 1982, revised 5 March 1983, accepted 23 April 1983

In the present communication the successive stability constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) of the complexes of N-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)-4-carbomethoxyaniline with some transition metals ions are described.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and methyl ester of *p*-aminobenzoic acid in ethanol. The product was repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure compound, m.p. 171°.

All measurements were carried out at 30 ± 0.1 . The pH meter used was Elico Model LI 15 with glass electrode designed for use over the pH 0.0 to 11.0 in combination with the dip type calomel electrode. The experimental details and computational methods were the same as described earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

The ligand used in this study did not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during titration and by the absence of any significant drift in the pH even after 1 hr.

In the ligand, it is the phenolic (OH) group that takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation the number of dissociable protons, Y, attached to each ligand molecule is one.

A curve between B values (pH meter readings) and corresponding \bar{n}_A values was plotted (Fig. 1) and the value of pK_1^H was evaluated from the half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. The plot of $\log(\bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs B was also drawn. From this pK_1 was evaluated. This value agrees quite well with that obtained by half integral method.

The $\log K_1$ value for Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Cd^{2+} systems were determined by half integral method, plotting the \bar{n} values against pL (Fig. 2). These

Fig. 1. Formation curve of N-[2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene]-4-carbomethoxyaniline.

values were further confirmed by the plots of $\log(\bar{n}/1-\bar{n})$ against pL . For Cu^{2+} system $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were computed by least squares method. The order of bivalent metal chelates was found to be $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+}$ which was in agreement with Mellor and Maley² order. The values are reported in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Metal ligand systems of N-[2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene]-4-carbomethoxyaniline.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SOME COMPLEXES OF N-(2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHALIDENE)-4-CARBOMETHOXYANILINE

	$t = 30 \pm 0.1^\circ$				
	H^+	Cu^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Cd^{2+}
$\log K_1$	8.76	7.76	5.08	4.78	4.14
$\log K_2$	—	6.84	—	—	—

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